

A Novel Method for the Pushout Test in Composites

Rebecca Sinclair and Robert J. Young

*Manchester Materials Science Centre,
UMIST/University of Manchester,
Grosvenor Street, Manchester, M1 7HS UK.*

SUMMARY:

The indentation or pushout test is a widespread method of evaluating composite interfaces. Pushout tests have been performed on three types of α -alumina fibre embedded in epoxy resin: Nextel 610, PRD-166; and Saphikon. It has been found that all three fibres exhibit a well-defined fluorescence spectrum consisting of two approximately Lorentzian peaks; and that when compressive strain is applied, the peaks in the spectrum shift towards lower wavenumbers. The shift, measured in cm^{-1} , is linear with respect to applied strain. The fluorescence spectra of the fibres were found to shift by approximately 8-10 cm^{-1} for each 1% of applied strain. This information was used to calculate the point-to-point axial strain variation in the embedded fibres. The fluorescence probe method of evaluating pushout tests is capable of producing sensitive and accurate information that is useful for understanding the stress distributions in the test.

KEYWORDS: Micromechanics, Pushout, Fluorescence Spectroscopy, Alumina fibres.

INTRODUCTION

The pushout or indentation test has become a widespread method for evaluating the interface strength of fibre composites.

Marshall [1] proposed an indentation method (also known as pushout or push-in) for measuring frictional stresses in ceramic matrix composites in 1984. A standard Vickers-type pyramid indenter was used to apply force to the end of a fibre, which is flush with the surrounding matrix in a polished composite specimen. The frictional force was calculated using the amount of slippage of the fibre end and the peak load required to produce it. Since Marshall's proposal, it has become possible to measure the load and force continuously throughout the test. Although in real use, most composites are not designed to undergo compressive loading, the test has become a popular method for evaluating the strength of interfaces in ceramic matrix composites and any composites containing fibres that are too brittle for pullout. As with the pullout test, it has become common practice to evaluate the effect of embedded length on the calculated strength of the interface. Conventional analysis calculates the average the interfacial shear stress, τ_a :

$$\tau_a = \frac{r\sigma_f}{L_e} \quad (1)$$

where τ_a is the average interfacial shear stress, r is the fibre radius, σ_f is the stress on the fibre and L_e is the embedded length. The analysis is essentially the same as Kelly and Tyson's analysis of the pullout test [2].

Fluorescence

Ruby and sapphire in their naturally occurring forms consist of high-quality α -alumina crystals with Cr^{3+} and other impurities. It is known that Cr^{3+} enters oxide lattices substitutionally and occupies sites of trigonal symmetry [3]. This causes level splittings in the ground and excited energy states, which show up in the fluorescence spectrum. Clear spectra can be obtained by stimulating the fluorescence with a single frequency light source. A typical spectrum for an oxide lattice containing Cr^{3+} or other ions in the $(3d)^3$ sequence has two well-defined peaks on a flat baseline. The shape of these peaks has been successfully modelled using a combination of Gaussian and Lorentzian functions [4]. Typical spectra are shown in Fig 1. It has been found that the application of stress on these crystals causes the fluorescence peaks to shift in frequency. This effect can be explained by cubic field theory [5,6]. Measuring the shift in the peak positions when known pressures were applied to a ruby crystal in a diamond anvil cell meant that the fluorescence lines could be used to measure stress [7].

Fig 1: Typical fluorescence spectra for the three fibres.

Measuring the stress in alumina based materials can be of use in composite testing in cases where the matrix material is transparent to laser illumination and fluorescent emissions. A number of optically transparent materials are suitable, for example epoxy resin (particularly Araldite LY5052) and E-glass. The fluorescence shift with applied stress is first measured in a single free fibre, and then the fluorescence spectrum of any position along an embedded fibre can be used to calculate the stress at that point. Fluorescence spectroscopy has been successfully used to analyse the fragmentation test in this way [8,9,10]. The use of fluorescence in the fragmentation test by Young and co-workers was based on earlier work with Raman spectroscopy [11,12,13]. This method has been applied to fragmentation, microbond and pullout tests.

Ma and Clarke measured the stress distribution along a short sapphire fibre embedded in an aluminium alloy matrix [14]. They achieved this by focusing a laser beam through an objective lens with a short depth of field into the fibre end. The beam was focused at successive depths along the fibre and the fluorescence measured at each depth using an optical microprobe. However, the depth of focus was not zero, so the measured frequency shift of the fluorescence was actually the average taken over the effective excitation volume. To solve this problem, Ma and Clarke measured the depth of field function of the microscope lens and used the results to perform a deconvolution algorithm on their results. Elastic field analysis was also used to resolve the contributions of radial and axial stresses to the measured stress.

The laser used in Young and co-workers' methods was plane polarised in the direction of the fibre axis, so that all the stress measured was axial. This enabled a simpler analysis than that of Ma and Clarke [14]. Pullout tests performed using Raman spectroscopy [13] have revealed that Cox's shear lag assumption can be used successfully to model the stress in all three tests before debonding occurs, and after debonding, Piggott and Kelly Tyson models can be used. Therefore it is proposed that the Cox model can be applied to pushout tests prior to debonding.

Cox [15] proposed a model which described the stress distribution of short fibres fully embedded in a composite. An important assumption of the model, known as the shear-lag assumption, said that the fibre contained only axial stresses and that shear stresses were concentrated at the interface. Cox also assumed that there was perfect adhesion between the fibre and the matrix. Cox's equations can be reinterpreted for the pullout test [16], and because of the similarity in the geometry of pullout and pushout tests, it can be used without alteration for this experiment. If a stress σ_{app} is applied to the protruding section of a fibre with radius r , there will be a stress σ_f in the embedded portion of the fibre that will decrease with distance x from the point where the fibre enters the block:

$$\frac{d^2 \sigma_f}{dx^2} = n^2 \frac{\sigma_f}{r^2} \quad (2)$$

The parameter n is given by:

$$n^2 = \frac{E_m}{E_f} \frac{1}{\ln(R/r)} \frac{1}{1+\nu_m} \quad (3)$$

where E_f and E_m are the fibre and matrix Young's modulus and ν_m is the matrix Poisson's ratio. R represents the radius of an imaginary cylinder of matrix around the fibre. Originally this was a fibre-spacing parameter but in single fibre model composites it loses its physical meaning. Since it is unmeasurable, R , or n as a whole, is simply adjusted to fit the results for each experiment.

With the assumption that there is no bonding across the fibre end, Eqn 2 can be integrated with the boundary conditions $\sigma_f = \sigma_{app}$ at $x = 0$ and $\sigma_f = 0$ at $x = L_e$ (the embedded length):

$$\epsilon_f = \epsilon_{app} \frac{\sinh[n(L_e - x)/r]}{\sinh[nL_e/r]} \quad (4)$$

where ϵ_f and ϵ_{app} are the fibre and applied strains, respectively. Eqn 4 is illustrated in Fig 2 (b) below.

Fig 2 Theoretical plots of the strain distribution in fibres during pullout using the parameters indicated. (a) The Cox model (full bonding). (b) The Kelly Tyson model (total debonding) [17].

The interfacial shear stress τ is obtained by taking the differential of the strain function in the fibre with respect to x :

$$\tau = E_f \frac{d\varepsilon_f}{dx} \frac{r}{2} \quad (5)$$

so from Eqn 4 and Eqn 5;

$$\tau = \frac{n}{2} E_f \varepsilon_{app} \frac{\cosh[n(L_e - x)/r]}{\sinh[nL_e/r]} \quad (6)$$

Eqn 6 is illustrated in Fig 3 (b) below.

Fig 3 Theoretical plots of the interfacial shear stress distribution in fibres during pullout using the parameters indicated. (a) The Cox model (full bonding). (b) The Kelly Tyson model (total debonding) [17].

Kelly and Tyson proposed a different model of the stresses in the pullout test [18]. They took the shear lag assumption, but assumed that the forces at the fibre-matrix interface were frictional only and that the interfacial shear stress was a constant, τ_f . This gave rise to a force balance:

$$F = 2\pi r L_e \tau_f \quad (7)$$

i.e. the peak force required to cause sliding F is proportional to the area of fibre surface in contact with the matrix and the interfacial shear stress. This gives rise to:

$$\frac{d\sigma_f}{dx} = \frac{-2\tau_f}{r} \quad (8)$$

and integrating Eqn 8 with $\sigma_f = 0$ at $x = L_e$ gives:

$$\varepsilon_f = \frac{2\tau_f (L_e - x)}{rE_f}. \quad (9)$$

Eqn 9 is illustrated Fig 2 (b) above. See also Fig 3 (b) for an illustration of the interfacial shear stress assumption. Later authors [19] defined the interfacial shear stress as:

$$\tau_f = \mu\sigma_0 \quad (10)$$

Where μ is the coefficient of friction and σ_0 is the radial stress acting on the interface.

EXPERIMENTAL

The pushout tests were performed on three types of α -alumina fibre embedded in epoxy resin: Nextel 610, a 12 μm diameter, smooth, polycrystalline fibre containing 99% α -alumina; PRD-166, an 18 μm diameter, rough, polycrystalline fibre containing 80% α -alumina and 20% zirconia; and Saphikon, a 130 μm diameter, single crystal fibre of industrial white sapphire. It has been found that all three fibres exhibit a well defined fluorescence spectrum consisting of two approximately Lorentzian peaks superimposed on a flat baseline; and that when compressive strain is applied, the peaks in the spectrum shift towards lower wavenumbers. The matrix material was a two-part resin consisting of 100 parts by weight of Araldite LY5052 resin to 38 parts by weight of Araldite HY5052 hardener, cured for 1 week at room temperature.

The fluorescence spectrum of the alumina-based materials was measured using a Raman microprobe system. This consists of a Spex 1403 Double Monochromator connected to a Nikon BGSC microscope, which has been modified to take laser radiation, and a 15mW Melles-Griot helium-neon laser. The system does not need to be modified to measure fluorescence rather than Raman scattering. The 632.8nm laser line is used to illuminate the specimen, producing fluorescence in the alumina fibre. The fluorescence is collected and separated into a spectrum in two stages by the two diffraction gratings of the Double Monochromator. It falls onto a charge-coupled device (CCD) which counts the number of photons of each wavenumber across the desired range. For alumina materials the range used was 14370 to 14460 cm^{-1} and the typical exposure time was 5s. All spectra were measured at a magnification of 50x. The signal from the CCD is collected by a computer, which plots intensity versus wavenumber and saves the plot as a spectrum file. Each spectrum file taken from an alumina specimen was fitted to two Lorentzian curves and a straight baseline using an

iterative fitting program supplied by Renishaw Raman System Software. The peak positions in terms of wavenumber of both curves were recorded.

To obtain calibrations of the relationship between R_2 peak shift and strain, single lengths of each of the three types of fibre were adhered to the surface of rectangular PMMA four-point bend beams. The beams were strained so as to place the fibre either in tension or compression. As the axial fibre strain was increased in steps, the position of the R_2 peak was recorded. The R_2 peak was found to shift linearly with strain. The peak was found to shift by 8-10 cm^{-1} for each 1% of applied strain.

This information was used to measure the stress distribution in single fibre model composites during indentation testing. The specimens consist of a length of fibre embedded horizontally in a 3 mm cube of cold-cured epoxy resin (see Fig 4). The fibre protrudes on one side, and stress is applied stepwise by pushing a flat block onto the protruding fibre end. At each compression level, the strain distribution is measured by taking fluorescence spectra at several points along the fibre.

Fig 4: The pushout specimen

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Example strain profiles from the pushout tests shown in Fig 5 to Fig 7 were fitted to Eqn 4 (the shear lag model for strain variation along a fibre). At zero applied strain, a version of Eqn 4 suitable for evaluating residual strain in fragmentation specimens [9]. For the Nextel 610 and PRD-166 specimens, the zero strain data was indicative of significant compressive residual strain, which indicates that there was resin shrinkage during the cold curing process. For Saphikon the zero strain data was indicative of zero residual strain. The difference between the three specimens may be due to the difference in the sizes of the fibres.

At applied strains above zero, the strain variation along the fibres was modelled by adding the appropriate strain profile at zero applied load to Eqn 4. The results are shown in Fig 5 to Fig 7 as solid lines. For the Nextel 610 and PRD-166 specimens the shear lag model (Eqn 4) provided a good fit. For Saphikon, Eqn 4 provided an acceptable fit; however, it would also have been possible to model the data using Eqn 9.

The modelled curves for each data set were differentiated to give an estimate of interfacial shear stress, τ_i using [20]:

$$\tau_i = \frac{E_f r}{2} \frac{d\varepsilon}{dx} \quad (11)$$

where E_f is the fibre modulus, r is its radius and $\frac{d\varepsilon}{dx}$ is the rate of change of measured strain

with respect to distance along the fibre. The interfacial shear stress profiles shown in Fig 8 to Fig 10 were calculated using Eqn 11.

Fig 5: Axial strain distributions obtained from a Nextel 610 fibre embedded in epoxy resin.

Fig 6: Axial strain distributions obtained from a PRD-166 fibre embedded in epoxy resin.

Fig 7: Axial strain distributions obtained from a Saphikon fibre embedded in epoxy resin.

Fig 8 Derived interfacial shear stress distribution for Nextel 610 pushout (data from Fig 5).

Fig 9: Derived interfacial shear stress distribution for PRD-166 pushout (data from Fig 6).

Fig 10: Derived interfacial shear stress distribution for Saphikon pushout (data from Fig 7).

CONCLUSIONS

- The fluorescence probe method of evaluating pushout tests is capable of producing sensitive and accurate information that is useful for understanding the stress distributions in the test.
- Upon application of compressive load on the protruding fibre of a pushout specimen, compressive axial strain increases at the point of entry of the fibre into the matrix. For Nextel 610 and PRD-166, the observed strain increase above the existing residual strain decays away to zero within 1000 μ m. For Saphikon, the compressive strain increase extends along the whole fibre length, becoming zero at the opposite end of the embedded fibre. The difference is likely to be due to the difference in fibre diameter.
- In most cases, the interfacial shear stress (ISS) profile in the pushout specimens exhibits a maximum at the point of entry of the loaded fibre into the matrix. In the case of the Saphikon specimen, the ISS profile is approximately flat at all applied strain levels.
- The maximum values of ISS were lower than the shear yield stress of epoxy resin (41MPa).

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors are grateful to EPSRC for supporting this work in the form of a studentship (RS) and a research grant (RJY).

REFERENCES

-
- [1] D B Marshall, 'An indentation method for measuring matrix-fiber frictional stresses in ceramic composites', *Journal of the American Ceramic Society*, **12** (1984) C259.
- [2] A Kelly and W R Tyson, 'Tensile properties of fibre-reinforced metals: copper/tungsten and copper/molybdenum', *Journal of Mechanics and Physics of Solids* **13** 329-350.
- [3] E Feher and M D Sturge, 'Effect of stress on the trigonal splittings of d^3 ions in sapphire (α -Al₂O₃)', *Physical Review* **172** (1968) 244.
- [4] R G Munro, G J Piermarini and S Block, 'Model line-shape analysis for the ruby R lines used for pressure measurement', *Journal of Applied Physics* **57** (1985) 165.
- [5] R M Macfarlane, 'Analysis of the spectrum of d^3 ions in trigonal crystal fields', *Journal of Chemical Physics* **39** (1963) 3118.
- [6] A L Schawlow, A H Piskis and S Sugano, 'Stain-induced effects on the degenerate spectral line of chromium in MgO crystals', *Physical Review* **122** (1961) 1469.
- [7] R A Forman, G J Piermarini, J D Barnett and S Block, 'Pressure measurement made by the utilization of ruby sharp-line luminescence', *Science* **21** (1972) 284.
- [8] X Yang and R J Young, 'Determination of residual strains in ceramic-fibre reinforced composites using fluorescence spectroscopy', *Acta Metallurgica et Materialia*, **43** (1995) 2407-2416.

-
- [9] R B Yallee, M C Andrews and R J Young, 'Fragmentation in alumina fibre reinforced epoxy model composites monitored using fluorescence spectroscopy', *Journal of Materials Science* **31** (1996) 3349-3359.
- [10] R B Yallee, 'Single fibre composite micromechanics', PhD Thesis, UMIST (1997).
- [11] I M Robinson, R J Young, C Galiotis and D N Batchelder, 'Study of model polydiacetylene/epoxy composites', *Journal of Materials Science* **22** (1987) 3642.
- [12] X Yang, X Hu, R J Day and R J Young, 'Structure and deformation of high-modulus alumina-zirconia fibres', *Journal of Materials Science Letters* **27** (1992) 1409.
- [13] R J Young, 'Evaluation of composite interfaces using Raman Spectroscopy', *Key Engineering Materials* **116-117** (1996) 173-192.
- [14] Q Ma and D R Clarke, 'Measurement of residual stresses in sapphire fiber composites using optical fluorescence', *Acta Metallurgica et Materialia* **41** (1993) 1817.
- [15] H L Cox, 'The elasticity and strength of paper and other fibrous materials', *British Journal of Applied Physics* **3** (1952) 72-79.
- [16] P S Chua and M R Piggott, 'The glass fibre-polymer interface: 1 - Theoretical consideration for single fibre pull-out tests', *Composites Science and Technology* **22** (1985) 33.
- [17] D J Bannister, 'Micromechanical and hydrothermal behaviour of single-fibre epoxy resin composites', PhD thesis UMIST (1996)
- [18] A Kelly and W R Tyson, 'Tensile properties of fibre-reinforced metals: copper/tungsten and copper/molybdenum', *Journal of Mechanics and Physics of Solids* **13** 329.
- [19] D K Shetty, 'Shear-lag analysis of fiber push-out (indentation) tests for estimating interfacial friction stress in ceramic matrix composites', *Journal of the American Ceramic Society* **71** C107.
- [20] A Kelly and N H MacMillan in *Strong Solids* 3rd Edition, Clarendon Press, Oxford (1980).